

Walk Up Aniene Dataset

Template: Horizon 2020

Dataset Description

1.2 Data Summary

1.2.2 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

["To share information", "To make informed decisions"]

1.2.3 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

["sensor data", "observational (e.g., sensor data, data from surveys)"]

1.2.4 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

[".txt files", "PDF", "RTF", "Stata", "gif", "tiff", "png", "mpeg", "mp4", "Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language)", "Numerical - SPSS, Stata, Excel", "Multimedia - jpeg / jpg, gif, tiff, png, mpeg, mp4, QuickTime", "Other"]

.shp (Shape file), GDB (Geodatabase)

1.2.6 What is the origin of the data?

["Primary data"]

1.2.7 What is the expected size of the data?

MB (megabyte)

1.2.8 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

["Researchers", "Decision makers", "Education", "The public"]

2.3 Reusable Data

2.3.1 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

No

3.4.2 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.4.2.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

```
[{"id":"metadataschema:rd-alliance/fgdccsdgm-federal-geographic-data-committee-content-standard-digital-ge","label":"FGDC/CSDGM (Federal Geographic Data Committee Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata)","source":"rd-alliance","uri":"http://www.fgdc.gov/metadata/geospatial-metadata-standards/"}]
```

3.4.2.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.4.2.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.4.2.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.4.2.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.4.2.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

No

Comment: we will not have different versions of our data

3.4.2.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for your data?

Yes

3.4.2.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.4.2.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for your data?

Yes

3.4.2.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Other

OpenAIRE

3.4.2.15 Will you use standardised formats for your data?

Yes

ZIP Format

3.4.2.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.4.2.21 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

Zenodo

3.4.2.22 Please describe if data require proprietary tools to access the data?

do not require proprietary tools

3.4.2.23 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.4.3 Making data openly accessible

3.4.3.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the data?

No

3.4.3.3 Will your data be openly accessible?

all

3.4.3.5 How will the data be made available?
["Project website", "Repository of Archive"]

Zenodo

3.4.3.7 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?
secure with backup and recovery

3.4.3.10 Are there any methods or tools required to access the data?
No

3.4.3.13 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?
no auxiliary data

3.4.4 Making data interoperable

3.4.4.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for your data?
Yes

3.4.5 Increase data reuse

3.4.5.2 When do you plan to make your data available for reuse?
end of project

3.4.5.5 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your data?
Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial 4.0 International

3.4.5.6 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of your data?
Yes

3.4.5.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes
["Other"]

3.4.5.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?
Yes

3.4.5.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?
Less than 2 years

4.5 Allocation of resources

4.5.2 How will the cost of making your data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?
["Other"]

4.5.3 Will you identify a data manager to manage your data, if not who will be responsible for the management of your data?
Yes

4.5.4 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the project data

Riccardo Leone

4.5.5 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

["Institutional archive"]

5.6 Data Security

5.6.1 What do you plan to do with research data of limited use?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.7 Ethical aspects

6.7.2 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.7.3 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

["Anonymising data where necessary"]

7.8 Other

7.8.2 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No